

Effective Detection and Recognition of Traffic Signs with Light Convolutional Neural Networks

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Abstract

Detection and recognition of traffic signs are two analytic processes in vehicular systems that contribute to increasing driver safety, warning, and preventing collisions by improving drivers' focus and awareness. They are also crucial for developing self-driving vehicles that can sense the environment through a camera eye and understand the road restrictions. Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) play an essential role in both processes by finding the traffic sign objects on acquired images or video frames and recognizing their meaning. However, CNN architectures running on vehicles need minimization, ensuring satisfactory performance and efficient operation with decreased computational resources. In this paper, we investigate two CNN architectures for traffic sign detection and two architectures for traffic sign recognition. Our experiments confirm that light models for both processes can successfully perform the achieved tasks, reaching effectiveness close to the complex models reported in the scientific literature.

Keywords: image recognition; object detection; artificial intelligence; traffic signs; Machine Learning; YOLO

1. Introduction

Advanced Driver Assistance Systems (ADAS) are a suite of technologies designed to assist the driver of a vehicle. The constantly increasing requirements for road safety are forcing the automotive industry to search for new and reliable solutions. Moreover, according to a report by the Austrian Institute of Technology GmbH [1], ADAS systems could reduce traffic accidents by several tens of percent over the next several years. Contemporary ADAS systems comprise a range of mechanical and electronic components, including sensors and recording devices. A key component of these systems is the microcontroller and the software that process the collected data and generate the appropriate signals to the actuators. Real-time operation is an essential property of ADAS systems, which requires the use of efficient data processing algorithms. These methods encompass solutions based on Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs), with a particular emphasis on deep learning (DL) architectures.

This work addresses a crucial aspect of ADAS systems: traffic sign detection (TSD) and recognition (TSR). We experimentally verified two sign detection methods (YOLO-based and Faster R-CNN) and two recognition approaches (ResNet50-based and our own light convolutional neural network, light-CNN). In addition, we performed a comparative analysis of the results obtained, emphasizing the efficiency and effectiveness of each solution.

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2. Related work

With the emergence of the idea of autonomous vehicles, the area of TSR became heavily investigated worldwide. Wali et al. [18] proposed a 3-stage system for detecting, tracking, and classifying signs. Color segmentation and shape analysis were used to localize, and neural networks and pattern comparison methods were used to classify. Despite an accuracy exceeding 90%, no details on speed were provided. Namyang and Phimoltares [12] tested a number of classical sign recognition methods (HOG, correlations, color descriptors) on Thai road signs. The results ranged from 26% to 93%, indicating the superiority of deep learning over classical methods. In practical test conditions, Babić et al. [3] demonstrated the weaknesses of production TSR systems. Only 21% of 1,071 modified signs (including obscured, damaged, and distorted) were correctly recognized by the systems installed in 17 different cars. Almost 73% of the signs were not recognized at all. Zhang et al. [23] developed the CCTSDB 2021 dataset, taking into account different lighting conditions. The best results in the tests were achieved by the YOLOv5 model - 76% mAP and over 120 FPS. The analysis showed that the detectability of traffic signs decreases when they occupy a smaller part of the image. Xing et al. [21] used guided image filtering to study fog and poor visibility. They used YOLOv5 and Faster R-CNN, achieving an accuracy of 90%. Zhu and Yan [24] explained how earlier methods based on color and shape analysis were limited by changing lighting and damaged signs. Their study compared the YOLOv5 and SSD models, showing YOLO's superior performance (98% mAP at 30 FPS) over SSD (90% mAP, 10× slower). The breakthrough was due to the use of neural networks to simultaneously detect and classify signs at high speeds. Megalingam et al. [11] developed the Refined Mask R-CNN (RMR-CNN) to recognize Indian road signs. It achieved 97% accuracy, but was biased by test images. Youssouf [22] designed a two-module system - a separate one for detection (YOLOv4, Faster R-CNN), the second one for classification (CNN). The detection models achieved 59% (YOLOv4) and 43% (Faster R-CNN) mAP, respectively, at 35 and 6 FPS. The classification module achieved 99% accuracy. Wei et al. [19] studied detection-free sign classification using convolutional networks and ResNet, achieving 98% and 99% accuracy, respectively. The signs were centrally located in the images, which significantly simplified the task. Ay et al. [2] took a similar approach, comparing AlexNet, DarkNET, and EfficientNET architectures, with the latter achieving the best results with a precision of 98%. Saxena et al. [15] applied the improvement in image quality (e.g., denoising and brightening) in combination with YOLOv4, testing the models on four different datasets. The best result was over 94% mAP (on the TT-100K dataset) and 32 FPS performance. For the tests with the MTSD data set, 80% mAP was achieved. This work complements the reported results by testing two world-renowned detectors in the TSR domain, investigating transfer learning in the TSR, and providing our own light-CNN model for the TSR process that works effectively and efficiently.

3. Materials and methods

In this section, we first focus on detecting traffic signs in images, presenting the preparation process for the models used (YOLOv8 vs. Faster R-CNN). Next, we introduce two traffic sign recognition models: one relying on transfer learning and the other using a light-CNN-based approach.

3.1. Detection of Traffic Signs

3.1.1. Detection with YOLO

The first of the models used for the traffic sign detection was YOLOv8 in the Ultralytics implementation [7]. The model was chosen due to its capabilities of tracking objects in video files, object segmentation, image classification, and real-time precision. Specifically, we selected the yolov8n model, which prioritizes the fastest possible operation and is the smallest of the object detection models available in the collection. With a relatively small number of parameters, this model achieves the best speed of operation, needing about 80 milliseconds to process the image [17]. To train the model, we used the Mapillary Traffic Sign Dataset [13]. The training set included 14,636 images, and 4,878 images in the validation set. The number of training epochs was 100. The results are presented in Figure 1.

Analyzing the results on the loss function graph (train/box loss, train/cls loss and train/df1 loss) during training, we can observe the values are decreasing rapidly, with smooth loss function curves for both the training data (train/box loss, train/cls loss and train/df1 loss) and validation data (val/box loss, val/cls loss and val/df1 loss). These charts show that the model stabilized and further training would not lead to a significant reduction of the loss value. Considering

Figure 1: Results of training of the YOLOv8n-based detection algorithm.

Figure 2: Cumulative loss function curves in training and validation for the Faster R-CNN traffic sign detection model.

the mean average precision plots (metrics/mAP50(B) and metrics/mAP50-95(B)), we also observe smooth increasing curves, which means that the model parameters reached values close to optimal.

3.1.2. Detection with Faster R-CNN

The second detection model used was Faster R-CNN in the Detectron2 implementation [20]. This network was prepared by the Facebook AI Research (FAIR) team to develop innovative solutions in the field of computer vision. In addition to the task of detecting objects in digital images, Detectron2 also offers advanced image segmentation and other functionalities. The faster rcnn R 50 FPN 1x model based on the ResNet-50 [14] network was selected for the developed traffic sign detector. The key aspects of the model selection were the network training speed and short inference time. To train the detection model, we again used the Mapillary [13] dataset. However, we did not use the entire Mapillary dataset, but only a subset - the training set contained 900 images (among them 4,343 contained instances of the traffic sign class), and the validation set contained 100 images (including 578 instances of the traffic sign class) due to the long training time and extended resources required for this purpose (compared to YOLOv8 training). The training was based on the following parameters: (i) the number of iterations equal to 1200, (ii) the learning rate equal to 0.0001, (iii) the batch size equal to 8.

Figure 2 shows loss function curves for the training and validation phases. Higher values can be observed for

the validation data, but from about the 600th epoch, both curves oscillate around certain fixed values. We can also observe a significant decrease in the values of the cumulative loss functions, which suggests correct model training.

3.2. Recognition of Traffic Signs

3.2.1. ResNet-50-based Recognition Model

The first idea for solving the problem of traffic sign classification was to use the popular ResNet-50 [14] architecture, known for its good adaptation to solving image classification problems. The default ResNet-50 network was initially trained on the ImageNet-1k [4] dataset consisting of a thousand separate classes, thanks to which the use of the basic ResNet-50 model allows for image classification into one of the predefined thousand classes. Although undoubtedly a valuable possibility, in the case of traffic sign classification, it is an insufficient solution - the traffic sign recognition algorithm assumes the classification of the object into one of many classes representing different types of traffic signs. The default ResNet-50 model does not allow for the classification of traffic sign types.

Therefore, we decided to rely on the transfer learning technique, which involves transferring knowledge gained while solving one problem to implementing solutions to other issues [10]. Here, we used an already-trained model when creating a neural network to solve the TSR problem. When doing it, we modified the dimensions of the input data and a set of network weights. The first parameter was set to $224 \times 224 \times 3$, which is the size of the input layer of the pre-trained ResNet-50 network; this value represented the dimensions of the input data (images). The imagenet configuration was selected as the values of the ResNet-50 network weights, which allowed us to use the knowledge from the previous model while training the model for the TSR problem. The basic ResNet model was supplemented with subsequent layers, creating a model for classifying an object into one of 43 classes. The diagram of the individual layers of this neural network is shown in Figure 3. It is important to note that all parameters of the ResNet50 model were locked before training. The first layer after the ResNet-50 model is Global Average Pooling, which is used to reduce each channel (dimension) of data to a single value by calculating the average of all values in this channel. This layer is used to transition from convolutional layers to fully connected layers, preserving the key features of the input data. The next is the fully connected layer (Dense) with 512 nodes. Each of the neurons of this layer is connected to each neuron of the previous layer, which allows for transforming and combining features, teaching the model complex, nonlinear dependencies. The activation function is ReLU. The next is the dropout layer (Dropout), which is used to randomly discard some of the neurons of the previous layer. The layer coefficient determines what part of all neurons will be excluded from the network. This operation is used to prevent excessive overfitting of the model. The last, output layer of the discussed model is again a fully connected layer (Dense) with an activation function softmax. The number of nodes of the last layer determines the number of classes into which the model divides.

To train the CNN network, we used the "German Traffic Sign Recognition Benchmark" [6] data set. In this data set, each image contains one traffic sign, occupying the entire image (excluding any background elements resulting from the shape of the traffic sign). For training the recognition models, the GTSRB set was divided into (i) the training set consisting of 26,466 images (~68% of the entire set), (ii) the validation set consisting of 3,921 images (~10% of the entire set), (iii) the test set consisting of 8,822 images (~22% of the entire set). The training parameters of the model based on the ResNet-50 network were: (i) the number of epochs equal to 30, (ii) the batch size equal to 32, (iii) the optimization method Adam [9].

Figure 4 presents graphs of accuracy and loss function over successive epochs of network training. Analyzing the accuracy graph, we can see a rapid improvement in the accuracy of the algorithm's predictions up to about the fifteenth epoch and a slow increase in the average accuracy in the remaining epochs. For both training data and validation data, a systematic increase in accuracy can be observed in successive epochs of training, which indicates that the model correctly uses the training set for learning. Similarly, the accuracy values for training and validation data suggest a correct generalization of the model - prediction of answers for data that the model does not use for learning. Considering the loss function curves, a successive decrease in the loss function value is visible in consecutive epochs, which indicates an increasingly better fit of the model to the training data.

3.2.2. Light-CNN-based Recognition Model

In the second approach, we assumed skipping the transfer learning techniques (and thus models initially trained for other tasks) and relying on basic layers of convolutional networks. We aimed to develop a compact and straightforward TSR model that preserves both prediction accuracy and precision. The created model is presented in Figure 3b. The

Figure 3: Layers of the trained traffic sign recognition models: ReNet50-based (a) and light-CNN (b).

most significant change compared to the first model relies on replacing the extended ResNet-50 model with a block of convolutional layers. Again, the input size to the network is $64 \times 64 \times 3$, representing the size of a flat image with channels responsible for colors. Two-dimensional convolutional layers (Conv2D) play a key role here, performing convolution operations on the input image. The first convolutional layer contains 32 filters, also called kernels, responsible for detecting various features in the image - edges, textures, and other patterns. Each filter has a size of 3×3 pixels - the filters pass over the image in blocks of this size, generating feature maps. The next layer after the convolutional layer is the MaxPooling2D layer, which operates on the results of the previous layer to reduce the dimensions of the previously created feature maps while preserving the most important information. The size of the sliding window on the image is 2×2 pixels, which results in halving the size of the data in each dimension (from 64×64 to 32×32). The main task of such a layer is to reduce the amount of data needed for processing, which is beneficial for the efficiency of the model and can prevent excessive overfitting. The pair of convolutional and max-pooling layers is then repeated, only increasing the number of filters in the second convolutional layer to 64. Both convolutional layers use the ReLU activation function. Right after the convolutional block, we placed a layer that flattens the multidimensional data maps to a one-dimensional feature vector (Flatten). This operation is necessary for the subsequent layers, which expect a one-dimensional input. The last block of the network consists of two fully connected layers separated by a Dropout layer. Similar to the previous model, the first fully connected layer has 128 neurons and a ReLU activation function. Subsequently, half of the neurons are randomly discarded, and the output fully connected Dense layer is activated by the Softmax function, where the number of neurons corresponds to the number of classes.

The designed model was trained, again, using the GTSRB dataset. We kept the same division of images both in

Figure 4: Accuracy and loss while training the TSR model based on ResNet-50.

Figure 5: Accuracy and loss while training a light-CNN-based TSR model.

terms of the size of the sets and specific images in specific sets, to provide the best possible conditions for comparing the performance of the models. The training parameters of the second model were: (i) the number of epochs equal to 30, (ii) the batch size equal to 16, (iii) the optimization method was RMSprop with a learning rate of 0.0001 [16]. Figure 5 shows graphs of accuracy and loss function in successive epochs of the model training. Accuracy for both training and validation data increases from the initial few percent to levels over 90%, which shows significant progress in model prediction after successive epochs of training. In the first ten epochs, the model rapidly increases its accuracy, after which the results stabilize. Similarly, in the case of loss function courses, initially, these values are high, but around the tenth iteration, they reach a value of 0.5. Graphs for validation data reproduce both the accuracy and loss function graphs for training data well.

4. Experimental results

Both approaches for traffic sign detection and recognition were tested experimentally to verify their effectiveness and time efficiency.

4.1. Detection of Traffic Signs

To test the effectiveness of both detection models, we used "The German Traffic Sign Detection Benchmark" (GTSDb) [6] dataset. It contains images collected on German roads, with annotations of road signs in the images. None of the images from the GTSDb dataset was used to train any of the models. The dataset consisted of 600 images, of which many images had more than one searched object - a traffic sign.

Table 1: Average values of YOLOv8n model metrics for the test set

	Metrics				No. detections
	IoU	Precision	Sensitivity	F1	
All detections	81.97%	55.21%	92.31%	69.09%	1683
Significant detections	82.80%	70.24%	84.01%	76.51%	1044

Table 2: Average values of Faster R-CNN model metrics for the test set

	Metrics				No. detections
	IoU	Precision	Sensitivity	F1	
All detections	83.47%	18.44%	95.94%	30.93%	6259
Significant detections	83.73%	29.21%	94.19%	44.59%	3804

YOLOv8: Table 1 presents the average metrics values collected while testing the YOLOv8n model. Two tests were performed - the first included all samples returned by the detection algorithm. In contrast, the second eliminated detections with a probability determined by the algorithm below 50% and detections smaller than 15 by 15 pixels. The second test aimed to eliminate small, false objects returned by the algorithm.

In both tests, we observed relatively high IoU and sensitivity values. A high IoU suggests that the trained YOLObased model was very good at finding objects in images, while a high sensitivity value suggests that the model correctly predicted most real objects. In the first test, the model coped very well with detecting real areas containing traffic signs but, at the same time, produced a large number of false regions (hence low precision). In the second test, in which we decided to filter out insignificant detections, a significant increase in precision was observed with a simultaneous decrease in sensitivity - the model predicted fewer real regions containing traffic signs but much less often identified areas falsely. The better balance of the algorithm’s performance in the second approach is also visible in the better F1 index value, reaching a result of over 76%. Analyzing the number of all detections, we can observe that without filtration, the algorithm returns significantly more traffic sign candidates, including false objects, which translates into metric values.

Faster R-CNN: The Faster R-CNN detection model was tested using exactly the same methodology and the same tools and datasets as the YOLOv8 model to ensure comparability of results. Table 2 presents the average values of metrics collected during testing of the Faster R-CNN model. The model detected real existing objects well, achieving an average IoU fit of 83%. Compared to the YOLOv8 model, the Faster R-CNN model returned significantly more detections in both tests. The sensitivity was over 94% - the model correctly detected the vast majority of real traffic signs. On the other hand, the model precision was very low. Despite correctly detecting real traffic signs, the model classified many false regions as searched traffic signs. Due to the large disproportion between sensitivity and precision, the F1 value is very low - in both tests below half. Filtering small objects with low certainty allowed for an increase in precision and F1 while avoiding a significant drop in sensitivity. In both studies, the average IoU was about 83%, which is just slightly better than the YOLOv8 model. The Faster R-CNN model performed much worse in the task of detecting road signs, and this is mainly due to the very high number of false detections.

Time Efficiency: The capability of the detection system to operate quickly is crucial for the real-time operation of the entire system. To investigate this feature of the algorithms, we decided to measure the detection times of traffic signs using 100 images from the GTSDB dataset. The images were checked one by one, and the measured time covered the period from passing the image to the detection model until the model returned the candidate images of traffic signs. The values of the average time needed for the detection algorithm are presented in Table 3. When analyzing the average runtimes of both models, we can see a huge disparity in their speed. The model using the Faster R-CNN architecture needed almost one and a half seconds on average to return objects. In contrast, the YOLOv8 model needed only six-hundredths of a second on average. By comparison, the faster model could process an average of 15 images per second, while the slower model needed about one and a half seconds to process just one frame.

After analyzing the results of the test of the average speed of detection models, we also decided to study the influence of the number of detected areas on the operating time. As shown in the previous tests, the Faster R-CNN model returned significantly more candidate regions, which could hypothetically explain the significantly slower

Table 3: Comparison of average runtime of detection models

	Model type	
	YOLOv8n	Faster R-CNN
Time, s	0.0634	1.48

Table 4: Comparison of average runtime of detection models for a varying number of detected traffic signs

	Number of detections in image					
	1	2	3	4	5	6
YOLOv8n	0.0559	0.0778	0.0682	0.0638	0.0668	0.0646
Faster R-CNN	1.45	1.46	1.47	1.46	1.47	1.47

performance of the model compared to the YOLOv8 model. To verify the validity of this thesis, the average operating time of the algorithms was also analyzed, considering the number of detections per image. The results of this study are presented in Table 4. Analyzing the test results, we can see that there is minimal or complete lack of correlation between both variables. Moreover, the Faster R-CNN algorithm needs about one and a half seconds to return objects, regardless of the number of regions detected by the model.

4.2. Recognition of Traffic Signs

TSR is a multiclassification task. Both models for TSR (ResNet-50-based model and light CNN-based model) were tested on a part of the GTSRB dataset. The test set included 8,822 images, each of which represented a traffic sign of one of 43 classes. Table 5 presents the class-averaged performance metrics collected while testing both models. The ResNet-50-based model achieved an average accuracy equal to 91.59%, which is a good result. The average model sensitivity of 91.59% suggests that the model effectively matches images to the appropriate classes, achieving a small number of false negatives. The average precision of over 91% indicates that the model rarely classifies samples into incorrect classes, which is particularly important - false positives are of particular importance in the case of traffic sign recognition in ADAS systems. High average sensitivity and precision also lead to a high F1 score, which is particularly important in the case of unbalanced data. Finally, Cohen's Kappa coefficient of over 91% suggests that the model achieves significantly better results than if the model were to be randomly selected.

The classification performance of the light-CNN-based model exceeded 98% in each metric. Compared to the first model, based on ResNet-50, there is a visible improvement in the overall performance of the light-CNN model. Another important aspect is the size of the model itself - the number of trained parameters and the size of the model stored on the edge device. These features are compared in Table 6. Both parameters are of great importance in terms of the created TSD/TSR system that works onboard the car - a smaller model size can result in faster operation and lower demand for computational resources. The first aspect is absolutely crucial in real-time systems, while the demand for computational resources can be of great importance for systems operating in vehicles, whose computational units may have low processing capabilities due to physical parameters. A small file size is more suitable for edge devices, as it allows for faster recognition of traffic signs. A smaller file with model weights requires less memory in the limited storage of the device and can also be upgraded more quickly during maintenance jobs. The size of the model and the number of parameters also significantly impact the training time of the model, which can be crucial in cases where the model needs to be extended with additional classes. As shown in Table 6, the model based on the ResNet-50 architecture has a significant number of untrainable parameters that belong to the ResNet subnetwork.

Table 5: Performance of TSR models achieved in the testing phase and the average classification time per traffic sign

	Metric					
	Accuracy	Precision	Sensitivity	F1	Cohen's Kappa	Time (s)
Res-Net-50	91.59%	91.79%	91.59%	91.61%	91.27%	0.0602
light-CNN	98.23%	98.28%	98.23%	98.23%	98.16%	0.0356

Table 6: Sizes of the tested TSR models (ResNet-50-based and light-CNN)

	Metric	
	ResNet-50-based	light-CNN
No. of all parameters	24,658,859	1,630,699
No. of trainable parameters	1,071,147	1,630,699
Model size	94.7 MB	6.22 MB

Table 7: Comparison of metrics for reported traffic sign recognition models

Model	Metric		Model	Metric	
	Accuracy	F1		Accuracy	F1
light-CNN (this work)	98.23%	98.23%	DarkNET [2]	94.69%	N/A
Wei et al.[19]	98.70%	98.00%	Youssef [22]	99.20%	N/A
EfficientNET [2]	98.64%	N/A	Inception [5]	99.57%	N/A
AlexNET [2]	97.45%	N/A	Khan et al. [8]	98.41%	98.42%

In real-time systems, the speed of each component is an absolutely key aspect, and the same applies to the onboard traffic sign recognition systems. To test the speed of the prepared classifiers, we decided to reuse the test set by recording the times needed to obtain the model prediction for 1000 test images. The results of the average time needed to obtain a response by each of the models are presented in Table 5 (Time column). The measurement method assumed measuring the time to get the model response of each sample separately, not the entire list of images at once. The goal was to obtain conditions as close as possible to those in which the system would work in a vehicle. The light-CNN model needed an average of only 35 thousandths of a second to make a prediction, while the model relying on the ResNet-50 network required almost twice as much time on average.

5. Discussion and Conclusions

In this study, we investigated the use of convolutional neural networks in traffic sign detection and recognition, applying a trained Faster R-CNN and YOLOv8 for the TSD, and ResNet-50 and our own light-CNN for TSR. We tested the approaches on publicly available datasets of images containing traffic signs, showing that all world-renowned models perform relatively well with possible cases of misdetections or false detections. Here, the nano model of YOLOv8 demonstrated slightly better detection capabilities and significantly better detection time than Faster R-CNN. This is a crucial conclusion for real-time systems, such as ADAS, installed in vehicles. Based on the experimental results, we can also see that transfer learning combined with additional training of the lower layers of the CNNs also works well. However, it results in building large and heavy models with many parameters. Therefore, we can successfully rely on simpler CNN architectures, like the light-CNN we proposed for the TSR problem. In this regard, this work complements the existing studies in the area. Table 7 presents a comparison of the average accuracy of traffic sign recognition systems using different approaches and neural network architectures.

All the presented studies were conducted using the GTSRB dataset. Analyzing the accuracy values, we can see that the light-CNN model presented in this paper achieves results comparable to those of other solutions that rely on convolutional neural networks. These results demonstrate that light CNN-based models for TSR can be as successfully applied as larger ones.

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